

PROFESSIONAL WELL-BEING OF PUBLIC SCHOOLTEACHERS: BASIS FOR WELL-BEING DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between teachers' demographic profile and their self-perceived well-being in public elementary schools in Porac West District, Division of Pampanga, during the school year 2024–2025. Employing a quantitative-descriptive and correlational research design, the study involved 185 public school teachers as respondents. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire that assessed teachers' profiles in terms of age, gender, highest educational attainment, position or rank, and years of teaching experience, as well as their self-perceived well-being across seven domains: perspective, self-management, supports, meaningfulness, self-care, practice competence, and professional development. Statistical treatments included frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and appropriate correlation analyses. Results revealed that most respondents were female, above 45 years old, had earned masteral units, were ranked Teacher III, and had 20 years or more of teaching experience. Overall, teachers reported a moderate level of self-perceived well-being across all domains. Findings further indicated a significant relationship between teachers' profile variables and their self-perceived well-being, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Based on the results, a well-being development program was proposed, emphasizing the promotion of a positive school culture, mental health support mechanisms, and self-care practices. The study underscores the importance of institutional support and targeted interventions to enhance teachers' well-being, which is essential for sustaining effective teaching and a healthy school environment.

Keywords: *teachers' well-being, self-perceived well-being, work-life balance, public school teachers, quantitative-descriptive research.*

INTRODUCTION

The modern educational landscape is characterized by rapid technological advancement, increasing complexity, and persistent stressors that significantly affect the psychological well-being of individuals, particularly teachers. Psychological well-being refers to a state of mental wellness that enables individuals to manage daily stresses, function productively, and contribute meaningfully to society. It shapes one's thoughts, emotions, and actions across the lifespan, from childhood to old age. The degree to which individuals experience psychological well-being depends largely on their perceptions of situations, personality traits, and the availability of support systems (Violago and Fabella 2023). In education, these factors become more pronounced as teachers navigate expanding roles amid constant change.

Psychological well-being is a core component of mental health that goes beyond the absence of illness, encompassing resilience, purpose, fulfillment, enjoyment, and life satisfaction. Tang et. al (2019) emphasized that understanding the underlying mechanisms of psychological well-being is crucial in promoting mental health and in developing effective, evidence-based intervention and training programs. In the teaching profession, such understanding is particularly valuable, as teachers' mental and emotional states directly influence their instructional effectiveness, professional commitment, and capacity to respond to diverse learner needs.

Teachers play a central role in shaping future generations and are regarded as the backbone of the educational system. However, the profession demands far more than classroom instruction. Teachers are expected to manage instructional planning, assessment, administrative paperwork, school designations, professional development, and constant interaction with students, parents, colleagues, and administrators. These demands contribute to the growing concern over teachers' work-life balance, defined as the equilibrium between professional responsibilities and personal life (Manalo and Velasco 2024). Teaching has consistently been identified as one of the most stressful professions, placing educators at heightened risk for burnout, emotional exhaustion, and declining well-being (Mingoa 2017).

In the Philippine public school context, teachers are confronted with excessive workloads and extensive documentation requirements that often encroach upon actual teaching time. Studies have shown that teachers are frequently overwhelmed by reports, instructional material preparation, and multiple ancillary roles, resulting in diminished performance and professional satisfaction (David 2019; Carnicer 2019). Such conditions contribute to chronic stress, emotional strain, and feelings of alienation from the school community, which negatively affect both teacher performance and learner outcomes (Sarabia and Collantes 2020).

The well-being of teachers is therefore essential to sustaining a positive classroom climate and ensuring quality education. Teachers' psychological, social, and professional well-being influences their ability to manage classrooms effectively, foster positive relationships, and support students' academic and emotional development. Research

indicates that stress management and mental health interventions, particularly mindfulness-based and cognitive-behavioral approaches, are effective in reducing teacher stress and burnout (Von Der Embse 2019). Moreover, teacher well-being has been shown to significantly affect students' engagement, behavior, and overall learning experience (Gragasin 2024).

Recognizing these concerns, the Department of Education has issued policies and initiatives promoting mental health and well-being among educators, particularly in response to the challenges intensified by the pandemic. Grounded in these realities, the present study investigates the well-being of public school teachers in Porac West District, Division of Pampanga, during the school year 2024–2025. Specifically, it examines how teachers' demographic profiles relate to their professional well-being and serves as a basis for proposing a well-being development program aimed at supporting teachers' mental health, work-life balance, and professional sustainability.

Research Questions

This study sought to find out if there is a significant relationship between the profile of teachers with their self-perceived well-being in Porac West District, Division of Pampanga during the school year 2024-2025. Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the public school teachers in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Gender;
 - 1.3. Highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4. Position/rank; and
 - 1.5. Number of years of teaching experience?
2. How may the professional well-being of public school teachers be described in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. Perspective;
 - 2.2. Self-Management;
 - 2.3. Supports;
 - 2.4. Meaningfulness;
 - 2.5. Self-Care;
 - 2.6. Practice Competence; and
 - 2.7. Professional Development?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of teachers and their self-perceived well-being?
4. What well-being development program can be proposed for the public school teachers?

Null Hypothesis

This study tested the following hypothesis based on 0.05 level of significance: There is no significant relationship between the profile of teachers and their self-perceived well-being.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative-descriptive and correlational research design to examine the self-perceived well-being of public school teachers in the Porac West District, Division of Pampanga, during the School Year 2024–2025. The design was appropriate for describing both the demographic and professional profiles of the respondents—specifically age, gender, highest educational attainment, position or rank, and years of teaching experience—and their level of well-being in terms of perspective, self-management, supports, meaningfulness, self-care, practice competence, and professional development. In addition, the correlational component of the design enabled the study to determine whether significant relationships existed between teachers' profile variables and their self-perceived well-being, which served as the empirical basis for proposing a well-being development program.

The respondents of the study were public school teachers currently assigned in the Porac West District, who served as the primary source of data. A researcher-constructed questionnaire was utilized as the main data-gathering instrument and consisted of two parts. Part I gathered information on the respondents' demographic and professional characteristics, while Part II measured their self-perceived well-being across the identified dimensions. The researcher personally administered and retrieved the questionnaires to ensure completeness and accuracy of responses. All collected data were carefully checked, coded, and tabulated prior to analysis.

Data analysis was conducted using appropriate statistical tools aligned with the objectives of the study. Frequency counts and percentages were used to describe the profile of the respondents, while weighted mean was employed to determine the level of teachers' self-perceived well-being using a five-point descriptive scale. To examine the significance of the relationship between teachers' profile variables and their self-perceived well-being, Spearman's Rho and the Chi-square test were applied. The level of significance was set at 0.05, and p-values were used as the basis for interpreting the results. Statistical computations were performed using Microsoft Excel and appropriate online statistical software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the data gathered and their analysis and interpretation to answer the sub-problems raised in the study.

Profile of the Public School Teachers

This section presents the profile of the teachers in the public schools in Porac West District in terms of age, gender, highest educational attainment, position / rank and number of years of teaching experience to answer sub-problem number 1. The data are presented in Tables 1A, 1B, 1C, 1D and 1E.

1.A. Age

The profile of the public school teachers in terms of age is presented in Table 1A.

Table 1.A.
Profile of Teachers in Terms of Age

Indicators	F	%
Above 45 years old	68	36.76
36 – 45 years old	53	28.65
26 – 35 years old	62	33.51
Below 26 years old	2	1.08
TOTAL	185	100%

Table 1A presents the age profile of the public school teachers and indicates that the largest proportion of respondents are above 45 years old, comprising 36.76% (68 teachers) of the total population. This is closely followed by teachers aged 26–35 years old at 33.51% (62 teachers), suggesting a substantial presence of relatively young professionals in the teaching workforce. Teachers belonging to the 36–45 age group account for 28.65% (53 teachers), reflecting a strong representation of mid-career educators. In contrast, only a minimal proportion of respondents are below 26 years old, with 1.08% (2 teachers), indicating limited participation of newly hired or early-career teachers. Overall, the findings reveal that the majority of teachers fall within the middle adulthood stage, with a significant concentration in their late 40s, highlighting a teaching force that is largely experienced and mature, which may contribute positively to instructional stability and professional expertise in public schools.

1.B. Gender

The profile of the public school teachers in terms of gender is presented in Table

Table 1.B.
Profile of Teachers in Terms of Gender

Indicators	f	%
Male	12	6.49
Female	173	93.51
TOTAL	185	100%

Table 1.B. presents the gender profile of the public school teachers and clearly shows a marked predominance of female respondents. Of the 185 teachers, 173 or 93.51% are female, while only 12 or 6.49% are male, indicating that the teaching profession in the public school setting is overwhelmingly female-dominated. This distribution reflects a long-standing trend in the education sector where women comprise the majority of the teaching workforce. As noted by Sebastian (2022), teaching is generally regarded as a female-dominated profession, a pattern that is also evident in the present findings. The data further suggest that female teachers play a central role in instructional delivery and in shaping the overall learning environment in public schools.

1.C. Highest Educational Attainment

Table 1.C. presents the profile of public school teachers in terms of highest educational attainment.

Table 1.C,
Profile of Teachers in Terms of Highest Educational Attainment

Indicators	f	%
Doctoral degree	1	0.54
Earned doctoral units	3	1.62
Master's degree	42	22.70
Earned masteral units	108	58.38
Bachelor's degree	31	16.76
TOTAL	185	100%

Table 1.C. presents the highest educational attainment of public school teachers and shows that the majority have pursued graduate-level studies, reflecting a strong commitment to professional growth. Most of the respondents have earned master's units, accounting for 58.38% (108 teachers), while 22.70% (42 teachers) have completed a master's degree, indicating active engagement in advanced professional preparation. Teachers holding only a bachelor's degree comprise 16.76% (31 teachers), whereas only a small proportion have reached the doctoral level, with 1.62% (3 teachers) having earned doctoral units and 0.54% (1 teacher) holding a doctoral degree. These findings suggest that teachers in the Porac West District recognize the importance of advancing their professional qualifications to enhance their effectiveness in teaching. Graduate education equips teachers with deeper knowledge of pedagogy, instructional strategies, educational philosophy, and educational technology, all of which contribute to improved teaching practices. Overall, the pursuit of advanced studies implies a strong determination among teachers to grow professionally, enhance instructional quality, and positively impact learners' academic outcomes.

1.D. Position / Rank

The profile of the public school teachers in terms of position or rank is presented in Table 1.D.

Table 1.D.
Profile of Teachers in Terms of Position/Rank

Indicators	f	%
Master Teacher II	5	2.70
Master Teacher I	9	4.87
Teacher III	116	62.70
Teacher II	12	6.49
Teacher I	43	23.24
TOTAL	185	100%

Table 1.D. presents the distribution of public school teachers according to position or rank and reveals that the majority of respondents occupy the rank of Teacher III, comprising 62.70% (116 teachers). This indicates that most teachers are already in mid-level positions, suggesting substantial teaching experience and professional development. Teacher I ranks second with 23.24% (43 teachers), representing those in entry-level or early-career positions, while Teacher II accounts for 6.49% (12 teachers). Only a small proportion of the respondents hold higher supervisory ranks, with 4.87% (9 teachers) classified as Master Teacher I and 2.70% (5 teachers) as Master Teacher II. Overall, the findings show that the teaching workforce is concentrated in the middle ranks, with relatively fewer teachers in senior positions. Consistent with the Philippine public school system, advancement in rank and corresponding salary grades is typically determined by years of service, educational qualifications, and performance, indicating that most teachers are progressing steadily in their professional careers.

1.E. Number of Years of Teaching Experience

Teaching experience matters with each year in the profession, hopefully leading to more student gains. The profile of the teachers in terms of number of years of teaching experience is presented in Table 1.E.

Table 1.E.

Profile of Teachers in Terms of Number of years of Teaching Experience

Indicators	f	%
20 years and above	51	27.57
15 – 19 years	30	16.22
10 – 14 years	38	21.54
5 - 9 years	41	22.16
Less than 5 years	25	13.51
TOTAL	185	100%

Table 1.E. presents the profile of public school teachers in terms of years of teaching experience and reveals that a considerable proportion of respondents are seasoned educators. Teachers with 20 years and above of teaching experience comprise the largest group at 27.57% (51 teachers), highlighting the strong presence of long-serving professionals in the teaching workforce. This is followed by teachers with 5–9 years of experience at 22.16% (41 teachers) and those with 10–14 years at 21.54% (38 teachers), indicating a balanced mix of early- and mid-career educators. Teachers with 15–19 years of experience account for 16.22% (30 teachers), while those with less than 5 years of experience represent the smallest proportion at 13.51% (25 teachers). Overall, the findings suggest that public elementary schools are staffed largely by mature and experienced teachers who have developed and refined their instructional skills over time. Teaching experience is widely associated with improved classroom practices and positive student learning outcomes, implying that as teachers gain experience, they become more competent in their field of specialization, thereby contributing not only to individual learner achievement but also to the overall effectiveness and learning culture of the school.

Self-Perceived Well-Being of Public School Teachers

This section presents the self-perceived well-being of public school teachers described in terms of perspective, self-management, supports, meaningfulness, self-care, practice competence, and professional development to answer sub-problem number 2. Tables 2A, 2B, 2C, 2D, 2E, 2F, and 2G present the data.

2.A. Perspective.

Table 2.A. presents the teachers' self-perceived well-being described in terms of perspective.

Table 2.A.
Teachers' Self-Perceived Well-Being Described in Terms of Perspective

Indicators	WM	DE
● Looking forward to going to work	3.37	MS
● Feeling calm	3.59	VS
● Enjoying my work with children and families, colleagues and other professionals	2.47	SS
● Being flexible and open to change	3.89	VS
● Having a workplace culture that cares about children and families	3.73	VS
OVERALL WM	3.41	MS
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Satisfied (HS)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfied (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Satisfied (MS)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Satisfied (SS)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Satisfied (NS)

Table 2.A. presents the self-perceived well-being of teachers in terms of perspective. Among the indicators, 'Being flexible and open to change' received the highest weighted mean of 3.89, described as 'very satisfied,' while the lowest was 'Enjoying my work with children and families, colleagues, and other professionals' with a weighted mean of 2.47, described as 'slightly satisfied.' The indicators 'Feeling calm' and 'Having a workplace culture that cares about children and families' obtained weighted means of 3.59 and 3.73, respectively, both interpreted as 'very satisfied,' whereas 'Looking forward to going to work' had a weighted mean of 3.37, indicating a 'moderately satisfied' rating. These results suggest that teachers who perceive high levels of well-being in terms of perspective are more likely to experience greater self-efficacy, job satisfaction, and openness to change, which can enhance their professional commitment and willingness to remain in the teaching profession. Improving workplace conditions and supporting teachers' professional confidence can further strengthen their sense of well-being, motivating them to engage more actively in their teaching roles, take calculated risks for growth, and adopt innovative practices in the classroom.

2.B. Self- Management

Table 2.B. presents the teachers' self-perceived well-being described in terms of self-management.

Table 2.B.
Teachers' Self-Perceived Well-Being Described in Terms of Self-Management

Indicators	WM	DE
● Making quiet time to complete tasks	3.68	VS
● Taking regular breaks during the workday	2.35	SS
● Having a workspace that is comfortable and comforting	2.68	MS
● Having influence in decisions affecting my job	2.73	MS
● Maintaining clear personal - professional boundaries	3.79	VS
OVERALL WM	3.05	MS
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Satisfied (HS)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfied (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Satisfied (MS)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Satisfied (SS)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Satisfied (NS)

Table 2.B. presents the self-perceived well-being of teachers in terms of self-management. The highest-rated indicators were 'Maintaining clear personal-professional boundaries' (WM = 3.79) and 'Making quiet time to complete tasks' (WM = 3.68), both described as 'very satisfied,' while the lowest was 'Taking regular breaks during the workday' (WM = 2.35), described as 'slightly satisfied.' Other indicators, including 'Having a workspace that is comfortable and comforting' (WM = 2.68) and 'Having influence in decisions affecting my job' (WM = 2.73), were rated as 'moderately satisfied.' The overall weighted mean of 3.05 indicates that teachers are moderately satisfied with their self-management practices. These findings suggest that while teachers demonstrate strong personal discipline and the ability to maintain professional boundaries, challenges arise in balancing work responsibilities with personal life, and in accessing sufficient opportunities for rest and decision-making influence. Supporting teachers in developing effective self-management strategies and providing resources to manage workload demands can help strengthen their well-being, resilience, and overall effectiveness in the classroom.

2.C. Support

Table 2.C. presents the teachers' self-perceived well-being described in terms of supports.

Table 2.C.
Teachers' Self-Perceived Well-Being Described in Terms of Supports

Indicators	WM	DE
● Having clear policies and procedures that support my work	3.36	MS
● Having helpful and debriefing available	2.78	MS
● Having the tools and resources to do a good job	2.45	SS
● Laughing and having fun at work	3.89	VS
● Having personal and social supports	3.42	MS
OVERALL WM	3.18	MS
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Satisfied (HS)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfied (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Satisfied (MS)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Satisfied (SS)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Satisfied (NS)

Table 2.C. presents the self-perceived well-being of teachers in terms of supports. Among the indicators, 'Laughing and having fun at work' received the highest weighted mean of 3.89, described as 'very satisfied,' while the lowest was 'Having the tools and resources to do a good job' with a weighted mean of 2.45, described as 'slightly satisfied.' Other indicators, including 'Having personal and social supports' (WM = 3.42), 'Having clear policies and procedures that support my work' (WM = 3.36), and 'Having helpful debriefing available' (WM = 2.78), were rated as 'moderately satisfied.' The overall weighted mean of 3.18 indicates that teachers are moderately satisfied with the supports available to them. These findings suggest that while social interactions and a positive work environment contribute to teachers' sense of well-being, gaps remain in terms of adequate tools, resources, and structured organizational support. Promoting teacher well-being through supportive policies, collaborative practices, and access to necessary resources is essential for enabling educators to effectively address the diverse psychosocial and learning needs of their students.

2.D. Meaningfulness

Table 2.D. presents the teachers' self-perceived well-being described in terms of meaningfulness.

Table 2.D.

Teachers' Self-Perceived Well-Being Described in Terms of Meaningfulness

Indicators	WM	DE
● Feeling safe (physically, culturally and psychologically)	3.33	MS
● Work that fits in well with lifestyle	2.37	SS
● Being myself at work	3.44	MS
● Having energy for work	3.42	MS
● Values that are aligned with the organization and the profession	3.67	VS
OVERALL WM	3.25	MS
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Satisfied (HS)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfied (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Satisfied (MS)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Satisfied (SS)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Satisfied (NS)

Table 2.D. presents the self-perceived well-being of teachers in terms of meaningfulness. The highest-rated indicator was 'Values that are aligned with the organization and the profession' with a weighted mean of 3.67, described as 'very satisfied,' while the lowest was 'Work that fits in well with lifestyle' at 2.37, described as 'slightly satisfied.' Other indicators, including 'Being myself at work' (WM = 3.44), 'Having energy for work' (WM = 3.42), and 'Feeling safe physically, culturally, and psychologically' (WM = 3.33), were rated as 'moderately satisfied.' The overall weighted mean of 3.25 indicates that teachers are moderately satisfied with the meaningfulness dimension of their well-being. These findings suggest that alignment of personal and professional values, a safe and supportive work environment, and energy for work are important contributors to teachers' job engagement, professional commitment, and overall workplace well-being. When teachers feel valued, safe, and connected to their professional values, it enhances their sense of competence, motivation, and satisfaction, ultimately promoting stability and effectiveness in their teaching practice.

2.E. Self-Care

Table 2.E. presents the teachers' self-perceived well-being described in terms of self-care.

Table 2.E.
Teachers' Self-Perceived Well-Being Described in Terms of Self-Care

Indicators	WM	DE
● Taking time at work to talk with co-workers	3.45	MS
● Work that meets my needs	3.30	MS
● Having regular breaks from work, including a longer one annually	3.41	MS
● Being fit and healthy	3.36	MS
● Earning sufficient money for my needs	2.45	SS
OVERALL WM	3.25	MS
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Satisfied (HS)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfied (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Satisfied (MS)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Satisfied (SS)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Satisfied (NS)

Table 2.E. presents the self-perceived well-being of teachers in terms of self-care. Four indicators—'Taking time at work to talk with co-workers' (WM = 3.45), 'Work that meets my needs' (WM = 3.30), 'Having regular breaks from work, including a longer one annually' (WM = 3.41), and 'Being fit and healthy' (WM = 3.36)—were rated as 'moderately satisfied,' while the indicator 'Earning sufficient money for my needs' received the lowest rating of 2.45, described as 'slightly satisfied.' The overall weighted mean of 3.25 indicates that teachers are moderately satisfied with their self-care practices. These findings suggest that although teachers recognize the importance of taking time for personal well-being, many prioritize work and caregiving responsibilities over their own health and rest. Promoting self-care is essential for maintaining mental, physical, and emotional health, preventing occupational stress, and supporting teachers' sustained effectiveness and resilience in the classroom.

2.F. Practice Competence

Table 2.F. presents the teachers' self-perceived well-being described in terms of practice competence.

Table 2.F.
Teachers' Self-Perceived Well-Being Described in Terms of Practice Competence

Indicators	WM	DE
● Being clear about my role and responsibilities	3.33	MS
● Achieving planned outcomes with those I work with	3.45	MS
	3.23	MS

● Contributing to prevention, social justice and social change	3.47	MS
● Working professionally, ethically	3.27	MS
● Being accountable professionally		
OVERALL WM	3.35	MS
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Satisfied (HS)
4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfied (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Satisfied (MS)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Satisfied (SS)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Satisfied (NS)

Table 2.F. presents the self-perceived well-being of teachers in terms of practice competence. All indicators were rated as ‘moderately satisfied,’ with the highest-weighted mean observed for ‘Working professionally, ethically’ (WM = 3.47), followed by ‘Achieving planned outcomes with those I work with’ (WM = 3.45). Other indicators, including ‘Being clear about my role and responsibilities’ (WM = 3.33), ‘Being accountable professionally’ (WM = 3.27), and ‘Contributing to prevention, social justice, and social change’ (WM = 3.23), also fell within the ‘moderately satisfied’ range. The overall weighted mean of 3.35 suggests that teachers perceive their professional competencies positively but acknowledge room for growth. These findings indicate that teachers’ sense of competence is closely linked to their effectiveness in fulfilling professional responsibilities, ethical practices, and contributions to social justice and school improvement. When teachers feel confident and competent in their roles, they are more likely to experience job satisfaction and commitment, whereas a lack of perceived competence could increase stress and turnover in the teaching profession.

2.G. Professional Development

Table 2.G. presents the teachers’ self-perceived well-being described in terms of professional development.

Table 2.G.

Teachers’ Self-Perceived Well-Being Described in Terms of Professional Development

Indicators	WM	DE
● Getting regular helpful supervision	3.40	MS
● Having regular opportunities for learning and development	3.35	MS
● Being professionally connected	3.30	MS
● Getting regular constructive feedback	3.23	MS
● Having goals or direction for my career	3.28	MS
OVERALL WM	3.31	MS
Legend: WM=Weighted Mean		
Point Values	Statistical Limits	Descriptive Equivalent (DE)
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Satisfied (HS)

4	3.50-4.49	Very Satisfied (VS)
3	2.50-3.49	Moderately Satisfied (MS)
2	1.50-2.49	Slightly Satisfied (SS)
1	1.00-1.49	Not Satisfied (NS)

Table 2.G. presents the self-perceived well-being of teachers in terms of professional development. All five indicators were rated as ‘moderately satisfied,’ with the highest-weighted mean observed for ‘Getting regular helpful supervision’ (WM = 3.40) and the lowest for ‘Getting regular constructive feedback’ (WM = 3.23). Other indicators, including ‘Having regular opportunities for learning and development’ (WM = 3.35), ‘Being professionally connected’ (WM = 3.30), and ‘Having goals or direction for my career’ (WM = 3.28), also fell within the ‘moderately satisfied’ range. The overall weighted mean of 3.31 indicates that teachers perceive moderate satisfaction with the professional development opportunities available to them. These findings suggest that access to supervision, learning opportunities, professional connections, and career guidance plays a crucial role in supporting teachers’ long-term professional growth, job satisfaction, and career commitment. Enhancing these aspects of professional development can foster positive attitudes, improve teaching quality, and promote teachers’ sustained well-being and effectiveness in the classroom.

Summary of Tables

Variables	WM	DE
Perspective	3.41	MS
Self-management	3.05	MS
Supports	3.18	MS
Meaningfulness	3.25	MS
Self-care	3.25	MS
Practice Competence	3.35	MS
Professional Development	3.31	MS
OVERALL WM	3.66	MS

As presented in the Summary Table, all variables were described as “moderately satisfied” with an overall weighted mean of 3.66 described as “moderately satisfied”. These results showed that teachers have positively exhibited moderate satisfaction towards professional well-being. Teacher well-being related to all aspects of working life, including the quality and safety of the daily environment, the climate at work and how teachers feel about both their school and the profession. Workload, relationships with colleagues, levels of connectedness and motivation, the work culture and physical environment, and sense of purpose can all help to shape a teacher’s well-being.

Relationship Between the Profile of the Teachers and their Self-Perceived Well-Being

This section presents the relationship between the profile of the teachers and their professional well-being to answer sub-problem number 3. The data are presented in Tables 3A and 3B.

3.A. Relationship between Profile and Self-Perceived Well-Being of Public School Teachers

Table 3.A. presents the relationship between profile of teachers and their self-perceived well-being along age, highest educational attainment and number of years of teaching experience.

Table 3.A.
Relationship between Profile and Self-Perceived Well-Being of Public School Teachers
(n=185)

	Spearman's Rho, rs	Descriptive Interpretation	p-value
Age and self-perceived well-being	0.3875	Positive Very Strong Correlation	< .00001*
Highest educational attainment and self-perceived well-being	0.5735	Positive Very Strong Correlation	< .00001*
Number of years of teaching and self-perceived well-being	0.6923	Positive Very Strong Correlation	< .00001*

**significant relationship at .05 level, **not significant relationship at .05 level*

Table 3.A. presents the relationship between the profile of public school teachers and their self-perceived well-being. The results indicate significant positive correlations between age ($r_s = 0.3875$, $p < 0.00001$), highest educational attainment ($r_s = 0.5735$, $p < 0.00001$), and number of years of teaching experience ($r_s = 0.6923$, $p < 0.00001$) with teachers' self-perceived well-being, all at a 0.05 level of significance, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. These findings suggest that older and more experienced teachers tend to report higher levels of self-efficacy and job satisfaction, likely due to increased professional competence, confidence, and sense of purpose. Similarly, teachers with higher educational attainment may experience greater professional growth and mastery, which positively influences their well-being. Moreover, extensive teaching experience enhances effectiveness and classroom management skills, contributing to overall emotional and mental well-being, although factors such as professional support and job satisfaction can further modulate this relationship.

3.B. Relationship between Profile and Self-Perceived Well-Being of Public School Teachers

Table 3.B. presents the relationship between profile of teachers and their self-perceived well-being along gender and position / rank.

Table 3.B.
Relationship between Profile and Self-Perceived Well-Being of Public School Teachers (n=185)

	df	Chi Square Statistic, χ^2	p-value
Gender and self-perceived well-being	4	26.44	.000317*
Position/Rank and self-perceived well-being	12	27.58	.00637*

*significant relationship at .05 level, **not significant at .05 level

Table 3.B. presents the relationship between teachers' profile and their self-perceived well-being, showing significant associations between gender ($\chi^2 = 26.44$, $p = 0.000317$) and position/rank ($\chi^2 = 27.58$, $p = 0.00637$) with well-being at the 0.05 level of significance. These findings indicate that both personal and professional characteristics influence teachers' perceptions of their well-being. Female teachers may experience higher levels of stress and emotional exhaustion due to greater emotional labor and work-life balance demands, whereas male teachers may report higher job satisfaction or self-efficacy. Similarly, a teacher's position or rank affects job satisfaction, professional identity, work engagement, and exposure to role-specific demands, with higher ranks potentially offering more autonomy but also increased responsibilities. Overall, the results suggest that factors such as resilience, self-efficacy, social-emotional skills, and workplace demands interact with gender and rank to shape teachers' well-being, influencing their engagement, professional effectiveness, and risk of burnout.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Most of the teachers are above 45 years old, female, have earned masteral units, are ranked Teacher III and have been teaching for 20 years and above.
2. Generally, the teachers are moderately satisfied which indicates a moderate level of contentment and fulfillment with their jobs. They are neither highly satisfied nor dissatisfied, indicating a neutral or average level of positive feelings about their work and work environment.
3. There is a significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and their self-perceived well-being; thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.
4. The proposed well-being development program for teachers focused on promoting a positive school culture, providing mental health support and encouraging self-care practices. It includes strategies like building strong

professional relationships, setting healthy boundaries and offering professional development opportunities related to well-being.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations were offered:

1. The proposed teacher development program should be considered for implementation to ensure healthy school environment.
2. There should be regular monitoring and evaluation of the proposed teacher development program for further improvement.
3. School administrators should continuously strengthen their supervision and professional development activities for all teachers to possibly maintain or even improve the level of teachers' competencies.
4. Other researchers may conduct similar studies on a wider scope to validate the findings of the study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study followed established ethical guidelines emphasizing integrity, respect, and accountability. Approval from relevant authorities and informed consent from participating principals were obtained prior to data collection. Participation was voluntary, with assurances of confidentiality, anonymity, and the right to withdraw at any time. All data were gathered and analyzed exclusively for academic purposes, ensuring accuracy, transparency, and fairness throughout the research process.

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